
AWARENESS AMONG TRIBAL PARENTS ABOUT EDUCATIONAL FACILITIES OF THEIR STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS

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Abstract

The study attempt to compare the awareness about educational opportunities of children with special needs of tribal parents with regard to their level of education and social setting. The sample for the study is total 150 tribal parents selected randomly for the study. An interview schedule for the parents is used to collect the information about the awareness of educational facilities of students with special needs. The major findings of the study are literate tribal parents were more aware about educational opportunities of their children with special needs than illiterate parents. Further, educated parents were more aware about the educational opportunities of children with special needs than illiterate parents.

Keyword: *awareness, educational facilities, students with special needs*

Introduction

Ours is a democratic set up, which relies on equal rights equal opportunities. So, to ensure that the disabled are accepted, respected and not discriminated upon in schools a follow up becomes necessary. Global figures estimate that approximately 15 percent of the population is disabled. So the educational opportunities of these disabled should be provided to them for their better development. Parents involvement, attitude and level of awareness is important for fulfilling the educational demand of children with special needs. So far the tribal parents are concerned, they are less educated, literacy rate among tribal people is very less as compare to non-tribal people, so these tribal community is not so aware about the educational opportunities of their disabled kids. Hence, the present study is undertaken to find out the awareness level of tribal and non-tribal parents about the educational opportunities of their children with special needs.

From the review of related literature and research studies it is revealed that very few studies have been undertaken so far in the area of special education especially on the parents of disabled children on India and abroad. Studies conducted by Blackard and Barsh (1982) on 'parents and professional perception of the handicapped child' impact on the family', Seligman and Meyerson (1982) undertook a study on 'Group approaches for parents of exceptional children and Penthol (2005) studied the developmental framework of guidance and counselling for the parents of the children with special needs and found that parental awareness is important for the education of their kids.

Odisha being poverty stricken state with a sizeable number of tribal population needs special attention of government and non-government sectors for the provision of education and needs based education for the employment of the children in general and children with special needs in particular for the economic and social development of the state. So the present study is undertaken to find out the awareness level of parents having students with special needs about their educational facilities.

Methods

Tools: The investigator developed interview schedule for the teachers. After the formulation of the questions, the investigator set the structure of questions in very simple and objective manners which were open and

close ended. The content of the information schedule for teachers was constructed and to seek information from the teachers of special and integrated schools. The investigator at the initial stage prepared a set of 20 questions. After consulting the subject experts, administrators and headmasters the content validity was found and 10 questions were retained in final draft and 10 items were dropped from the interview schedule for the teachers of the schools.

Table-1

Significance of difference between illiterate and literate tribal parents on awareness about educational opportunities of their children with special needs

Group of parents	N	Mean	SD	SED	t-ratio	Level of significance
Illiterate	50	77.67	3.45	0.71	5.55	.01**
Literate	50	81.61	3.67			

The Table-1 revealed that the mean scores of illiterate and literate tribal parents on awareness about the educational opportunities of their children with special needs are 77.67 and 81.61 with SDs 3.45 and 3.67 respectively. The t-ratio came out from the above two groups is 5.55 which is significant at .01 level of significance. That means there is significant difference between above two groups on awareness about educational opportunities of children with special needs. Moreover, the mean scores of literate tribal parents is higher than illiterate parents. It indicates that literate parents were more aware about the educational opportunities of their children with special needs than illiterate parents. Thus the hypothesis (H-1) that the 'literate tribal parents were more aware about educational opportunities of their children with special needs than illiterate parents' is accepted.

Mean scores of illiterate and literate tribal parents on educational opportunities for their children with special needs as depicted in table-1 is represented by the bar Fig. 1

Table-2

Significance of difference between illiterate and educated tribal parents on awareness educational opportunities of their children with special needs

Group of parents	N	Mean	SD	SED	t-ratio	Level of significance
Illiterate	50	77.67	3.45	0.74	6.46	.01
Educated	50	82.45	4.01			

The Table 4.27 revealed that the mean scores of illiterate and educated tribal parents on awareness about the educational opportunities of their children with special needs are 77.67 and 82.45 with SDs 3.45 and 4.01 respectively. The t-ratio came out from the above two groups is 6.46 which is significant at .01 level of significance. That means there is significant difference between above two groups on awareness about educational opportunities of their children with special needs. However, the mean scores of educated tribal parents is higher than illiterate parents. It indicates that educated parents were more aware about the educational opportunities of children with special needs than illiterate parents.

Thus the hypothesis (H-2) that the 'educated tribal parents were more aware about educational opportunities of their children with special needs than illiterate parents' is accepted.

Mean scores of illiterate and literate tribal parents on educational opportunities for their children with special needs as depicted in table 4.27 is represented by the bar Fig. 2

Table-4.28

Significance of difference between literate and educated tribal parents on awareness about educational opportunities of their children with special needs

Group of parents	N	Mean	SD	SED	t-ratio	Level of significance
Literate	50	81.61	3.67	0.76	1.11	Not sig.
Educated	50	82.45	4.01			

The Table 4.28 revealed that the mean scores of literate and educated tribal parents on awareness about educational opportunities of their children with special needs are 81.61 and 82.45 with SDs 3.67 and 4.01 respectively. The t-ratio came out from the above two groups is 1.11 which is not significant at both level of significance. That means there is no significant difference between above two groups on awareness about educational opportunities of children with special needs. However, the mean scores of educated tribal parents is higher than literate parents. It indicates that educated parents were more aware about the educational opportunities of their children with special needs than literate parents.

Thus the hypothesis (H-3) that the 'educated tribal parents were more aware about educational opportunities of their children with special needs than literate parents' is rejected.

Mean scores of literate and educated tribal parents on educational opportunities for their children with special needs as depicted in table 4.28 is represented by the bar Fig. 3

Findings and Discussion

There is a significant difference among tribal parents about awareness about educational facilities of their students with special needs. So far educated parents are concerned they were more aware about the educational facilities than literate parents. Further, literate parents were more aware than the illiterate parents about the awareness of educational facilities of their children. Educational level of parents plays a significant role to get awareness about educational facilities of disabled. So it is suggested that authority, administrator, stakeholders should create awareness about different facilities of disabled among illiterate parents through mass media, poster and drama (nukkad). There should be arranged parents meeting. Participate workshop, seminar about disability to make them aware.

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